

Compound of the type (I) might also be active against fungi. Such compounds have

group which is perhaps responsible for their fungicidal activity. All the compounds of this series gave characteristic red colour with conc. H_2SO_4 .

Experimental

All the melting points have been determined on a Kofler instrument and are uncorrected. The I.R. spectra were determined with a Perkin-Elmer infra-red model-577 using KBr disc.

The general procedure adopted for the preparation of thiazoline diones is as given below :

A mixture of chloranil (0.1 mole), substituted ammonium dithiocarbamates (0.2 mole), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.8 g) in ethanol (25 ml) were heated under reflux on a steam bath for about 6 hrs. The coloured solid was washed with water, sodium carbonate solution and then dried. It was recrystallised twice from DMF-ethanol. The purity of products was established by analyses and TLC. The analysis, m.p., I.R. data, etc., are given in Table 1.

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Melting of Nitrophenols and Nitrotoluenes

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VASUDEVAN and Beddoes¹ studied zone melted sample of *m*-nitrophenol (MNP) and established that it exists in two different crystal modifications. Also interesting properties were noted in the melt and supercooled regions. We report here the dilatometric data in these regions for *o*-*m*- and *p*-nitrophenols and *p*-nitrotoluene.

Experimental

The compounds were purified by methods described in the literature^{2,3}. The solids were subjected to repeated recrystallisation. MNP was further purified by zone-melting. IR spectra of the samples were recorded for purity check. Densities of the melts were determined by a pipette type of pycnometer⁴. Volume changes on melting and in the post melt region were measured in a specially designed dilatometer containing a weighed sample. All the trapped air was released by repeated melting and freezing under vacuum. Ultimately mercury was filled over the sample and its level served as reference. The dilatometer was placed in a thermostat for thermal equilibrium, the temperature being controlled to $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The cryoscopic constant K_f of the compounds under study was determined, using purified naphthalene as the solute.

Results and Discussion

The volume changes in the premelting, melting and post-melting regions up to 20° above the melting point were recorded.

The density (ρ) of the compounds above the melting point is linear with temperature (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Density of Nitrophenol Melts at Various Temperatures.

The ratio $\frac{d\rho}{dT}$ is in the expected range of $(8.0-9.0) \times 10^{-4}$. Bondi⁵ suggested that packing density (ρ^*) be defined by $\frac{\rho V_w}{M} = \frac{V_w}{V}$, where V_w is the van der Waal molar volume and V , the actual volume. This

reduced density (ρ^*) can be chosen as a convenient reduced parameter for comparing the nature of packing in liquids. Such a procedure brings the density of the liquids into a comparable magnitude range. We have calculated V_w from the bond distances and van der Waal radii tabulated by Bondi⁶. The packing density for all the compounds just above the melting point fall in the expected range of 0.64 predicted for low temperature packing of spherical molecules under atmospheric pressure, i.e., the compounds are at corresponding states. Bondi⁶ defined a reduced

parameter $T^* = \frac{5cRT}{E_{\text{vap}}}$, where E_{vap} is the energy of vaporisation at a standard state defined as the temperature at which $\frac{V}{V_w} = 1.70$. The number of degrees

of freedom (3c) of a polyatomic molecule reduces to a value of 6 for rigid molecules. Plot of ρ^* versus T^* in the case of non-linear rigid molecules are expected to fall on one line. Plot of our experimental ρ^* - data for nitrotoluenes⁶, (Fig. 2) is linear with T^* ,

Fig. 2. Reduced Density of Nitrotoluene Melts at Various Temperatures.

within the accuracy with which V_w and E_{vap} could be computed. Thus in the liquid state immediately above their melting point, these compounds behave normally in spite of expected strong intermolecular interactions. In fact, there is no difference between the *o*-isomer, where intramolecular hydrogen bonding should be significant and the *m*- and *p*-isomers, where intermolecular interactions should predominate. This means that the type of associations formed have little bearing on the packing.

The volume changes on melting along with ΔH_m and $\Delta S_m/R$ values obtained by cryoscopy are given in Table 1. All the compounds under study show a

TABLE 1— ΔV_m , ΔH_m AND $\Delta S_m/R$ VALUES

Compounds	ΔV_m ml/mole	ΔH_m K cal/mole	$\Delta S_m/R$
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	9.10	3.73	5.90
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenol	9.3	4.83	6.60
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	9.0	4.82	6.27
<i>p</i> -Nitrotoluene	9-10	3.68	5.71

$\Delta V_m \sim 9-10$ ml/mole. Thus studies on thermodynamics of melting and packing as indicated by density measurements do not seem to reflect the differences between the isomers.

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Solubilization of 9, 10 Diphenyl anthracene in Surfactant Micelle with the Help of Fluorescence Studies

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IN this communication we report solubilization studies of 9, 10 diphenylanthracene (9, 10 DPA) in presence of surfactants with the help of fluorescence spectroscopy. Preliminary observations have already been reported earlier¹ in which it was shown that enhancement in fluorescence of 9, 10 DPA takes place on the addition of surfactants.

It has been found by fluorescence studies that anionic, cationic as well as non-ionic surfactants have solubilizing influence on 9, 10 DPA. Addition of ethanol also causes enhancement in fluorescence intensity of 9, 10 DPA.

Experimental

Fluorescence studies were made on Aminco-Bowman spectrofluorophotometer with Xenon arc